

OPERAS

open scholarly communication in the european
research area for social sciences and humanities

**Ensuring Local Needs & Strengthening
Distributed Infrastructures:**

OPERAS National Nodes

OPERAS Community: Policy Brief

August 2025

This policy brief highlights the importance of OPERAS' National Nodes as a means to support open scholarly communication at both the country and European levels in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). National Nodes serve as key connection points with local communities, acting as structural mediators within various infrastructures and organisations supported by the European Commission. The nodes ensure that local needs and perspectives are integrated into broader European initiatives, thus facilitating the internationalisation of research without losing diverse cultures, languages and traditions of scholarly practices.¹

¹ The importance of national contact points are common in a lot of European structures, as well as in [Horizon Europe](#) itself.

▶ 1. A Key to Strengthening Distributed Infrastructures - the need for OPERAS National Nodes

OPERAS research infrastructure (RI) supports open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area (ERA). Established as an international not-for-profit association (AISBL) under Belgian law in 2019, it was added to the ESFRI Roadmap² in 2021. OPERAS is on the path to becoming an ERIC, a process to be concluded in 2027 and supported by the OPERAS-PLUS project³. A central element of OPERAS' governance is the establishment of National Nodes, which are key to effective community management and to achieving OPERAS' objectives. To guide this process, the OPERAS National Nodes Roadmap⁴ outlines a common approach to the 13 OPERAS National Nodes for engaging communities and providing OPERAS services nationally with four guiding principles:

- ▶ Increasing awareness of OPERAS nationally;
- ▶ Building strong networks among relevant stakeholders;
- ▶ Understanding the specific needs of potential partners;
- ▶ Tailoring the dissemination of OPERAS services to meet those needs.

This guarantees that National Nodes are responsive to local contexts while aligned with OPERAS' mission.

Sustainable local funding, particularly for human resources, is a prerequisite for this model to succeed. Ensuring this support for the National Nodes is essential to advance open scholarly communication in SSH across the ERA as they play a key role in supporting OPERAS' mission to make Open Science a reality for SSH research. **Such investment supports not only the OPERAS infrastructure but also the broader objective of promoting research excellence and openness within the ERA.**

***OPERAS** is the only research infrastructure that addresses open scholarly communication for SSH. OPERAS is distributed and collaborative, it is run by and for the community. It works closely with other European Research Infrastructures, particularly DARIAH, CLARIN, and CESSDA, to identify overlaps and to seek opportunities to work together on a range of projects, such as those funded under Horizon Europe and linked to EOSC. OPERAS is developing tools and services stemming from SSH but relevant and useful for all scientific disciplines. It also promotes interdisciplinarity and the development of standards and recommendations, such as the Action Plan for Diamond Open Access⁵, which are particularly important for other disciplines and the broader research landscape. This led to the establishment of the European Diamond Capacity Hub in January 2025, with OPERAS serving as its fiscal host.*

2 ESFRI Roadmap: <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/>

3 See more details about the project OPERAS-PLUS: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079608>

4 The National Node Roadmap was developed in Work Package 7 of the OPERAS-PLUS project, available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289238>. This first version was issued in 2023, and a final version of the National Nodes Roadmap was delivered in May 2025, see <https://zenodo.org/records/15533121>

5 More about the [Action Plan for Diamond Open Access](#)

Recommendations for Strengthening OPERAS National Nodes

To sustain the impact of the National Nodes, ensuring they effectively contribute to national priorities and maintain interconnectivity between infrastructures and research communities within SSH, we recommend the following:

Establish a Structured Dialogue

We invite National Ministries to engage in a structured dialogue and regular interaction with their relevant OPERAS National Nodes to explore opportunities for collaboration in strengthening the National Nodes and enabling continuous alignment with national priorities. A joint approach will enhance their role in advancing national interests.

Foster Strategic Partnerships and Goals

We propose that the Ministries support their National Node by identifying key areas and actors to maximise impact. Thereby, recognising the value that OPERAS National Nodes bring to each country.

Enhance Financial Support

We encourage National Ministries to explore long-term funding solutions, including potential membership in OPERAS ERIC, to help secure their continued impact and success. Sustainable resourcing is essential for the effective operation of the National Nodes.

By working together, we can strengthen the National Nodes and reinforce their pivotal role in achieving the connection between the European and national infrastructures.

2. OPERAS National Nodes: Examples of National Impact and Integration

National Nodes facilitate bidirectional integration. This approach ensures specific local needs are acknowledged, discussed and integrated into OPERAS RI, while overarching recommendations, resources and services are tailored to the unique needs of each national research community, fostering both scalability and collaboration.

Within OPERAS, 13 National Nodes are already operational. In the following section, a number of examples are grouped into themes to highlight where the work of the Nodes has had a sound impact on the national landscape.

Enhancing the Visibility and Reach of National Initiatives and Services

Initiatives

OPERAS provides a unique place for connecting small publishers, libraries, researchers, infrastructure providers and other stakeholders. It enables initiatives and services to flourish on a European level, where knowledge and resources are shared, strengthening ongoing activities that benefit the open scholarly communication community. By supporting communities and initiatives, OPERAS National Nodes foster connections with institutions and promote collaboration across the scholarly landscape nationally.

The **Open Access Books Network (OABN)** began as an informal network to foster dialogue around open access (OA) books. It was created by OAPEN, Open Book Publishers, and SPARC Europe. These organisations are part of the UK and Dutch nodes of OPERAS: **OPERAS-UK**, led by Jisc, and **OPERAS-NL**, led by OAPEN. In 2023, it became a Special Interest Group within the OPERAS infrastructure and is now one of the working groups of the Special Interest Group *Open Access Books*. It serves a global community, connecting publishers, researchers, librarians, and infrastructure providers dedicated to equitable and accessible OA book publishing. Through activities such as workshops, webinars, blogs, and interactive discussion forums, the OABN has become a vital space for knowledge-sharing and best-practice development.

Services

OPERAS coordinates and federates resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH. Therefore, OPERAS integrates services into its service catalogue and sustains their development. As a distributed infrastructure, OPERAS not only creates new services but also builds on existing ones, scaling them up from a national to a European and international level. OPERAS National Nodes act as facilitators in identifying national resources.

The **Peer Review Information Service for Monographs (PRISM)**, operated by **OAPEN on behalf of the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB)**, became part of the OPERAS services catalogue in 2019. This integration allowed for migration to improved software, enhancing user experience and expanding outreach to a broader audience. OPERAS and other National Nodes could promote PRISM more effectively in their countries. For example, the German

National Node **OPERAS-GER**, led by the **Max Weber Foundation**, raised awareness of PRISM through collaborative events, resulting in 25 new German DOAB publishers in 2021, over 1.3 million OA book downloads (15% of global traffic), and a 2023 service-level agreement of OAPEN to host DFG-funded books.

National Nodes such as **OPERAS-PT** (the Portuguese node led by the **University of Coimbra**), are providing expertise for specific topics that are particularly important and addressing needs within the open scholarly communication community in SSH. OPERAS-PT is contributing its expertise on Multilingualism through its work as a leader of the OPERAS Special Interest Group on Multilingualism and initiated the creation of a new translation service, **Mondaecus**, to support collaborative work that brings together translators, proofreaders and subject matter experts to deliver high-quality translations.

▶ Internationalisation & Strengthening Collaboration within National Infrastructures

By operating as a National Node, OPERAS contributes to national developments and integrates them at the European level by connecting resources, developments, and infrastructures across national and European contexts. National infrastructure systems often face challenges in internationalising their activities, but OPERAS National Nodes provide critical support to make this goal achievable.

The construction of the Italian National Node, **OPERAS-IT**, has been a significant development as it was constituted within a remarkably short period of 12 months, triggering a significant interest from other infrastructures, institutions, and individuals to engage and commit to the consortium. The formation of H2IOSC (Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud), a joint project of the national nodes of CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it, and OPERAS-IT is seeking to create a collaborative cluster of European distributed research infrastructures involved in the humanities and cultural heritage sectors with operating nodes across Italy. The consortium also made possible a cooperation to organise a successful technology event with the Horizon Europe-funded CRAFT-OA project⁶, where OPERAS is also a partner.

With the ongoing developments of the NFDI (National Research Data Infrastructure) in Germany, **OPERAS-GER** is integrated as a key player within the SSH, contributing to the internationalisation of their activities. OPERAS-GER is positioned alongside CLARIN and DARIAH within the GKFI e.V., forming part of the SSH research infrastructures and enabling the alignment of activities, and is also actively involved in consortia of the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). Furthermore, the integration of BASE (with over 400 million records from more than 11,000 content providers) into the GoTriple platform, along with access to 2.7 million open access publications from the German National Library (DNB), exemplifies OPERAS' commitment to expanding discoverability and interoperability in the open scholarly ecosystem.

⁶ CRAFT-OA (Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access): <https://www.craft-oa.eu/>. Grant Agreement no. 101094397

The Slovenian national node **OPERAS-SI, led by ZRC SAZU (Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts)**, was founded in December 2024 as a consortium of six members. It consists of the three largest Slovenian universities, two SSH research institutions and the university library of Ljubljana. All members of the consortium are also active in the Slovenian Open Science Community ([SSOZ](#)), which includes all relevant stakeholders (RPOs and RFOs), also from the STEM field. SSOZ has already entrusted OPERAS-SI with the coordination of activities related to increasing the quality and visibility of academic publishing. OPERAS-SI is currently compiling a list of Slovenian scientific journals (in conjunction with the activities of the project CRAFT-OA and the European Diamond Capacity Hub⁷) and organising several workshops to promote the use of Open Journals Systems (OJS⁸).

▶ Triggering New Discussions & Establishing Best Practices

National Nodes play a key role in transferring European recommendations into action, raising awareness, informing and initiating new discussions within countries where gaps exist. National aspects, such as the development of regional or thematic infrastructures, can be more precisely addressed within the National Nodes.

While internationalisation has brought clear benefits, it has also reinforced English as the dominant language—especially in STEM. Yet in many SSH disciplines, native languages remain essential to the research process. Preserving linguistic diversity while ensuring global visibility requires dedicated multilingual infrastructures. OPERAS National Nodes are key in this effort, enabling local engagement, supporting research in national languages, and aligning with European open science strategies. Additionally, workshops, presentations, and training can be conducted in national languages to reach a wider audience and make the OPERAS research infrastructure and European developments within the SSH and open scholarly communication more accessible.

The Polish National Node, **OPERAS-PL (led by IBL PAN)**, created a *Manifesto of Open Humanities* that initiated discussions on the role of open science in humanities research assessment. Through various events organised as part of OPERAS-PL's National Node activities, the need for clear guiding principles was highlighted and discussed with various stakeholders: research institutions, librarians, publishers and policymakers. This manifesto serves as a call to action, advocating for the inclusion of open science principles in research assessment, funding for publishers and investment in open scholarly communication infrastructure.

In Croatia, the **University of Zadar** serves as the National Node (**OPERAS-HR**), facilitating the implementation of European developments into institutional and national standards through more direct and streamlined access. For example, the University Publishing Office is implementing standards from DIAMAS and OPERAS services such as PRISM into its systems. OPERAS-HR, like many other National Nodes, is advocating for European initiatives such as support for the Barcelona Declaration.

⁷ The European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) aims to strengthen the Diamond OA community in Europe by supporting European institutional, national and disciplinary capacity centres, Diamond publishers and service providers in their mission of Diamond OA scholarly publishing. The EDCH is fiscally hosted by OPERAS. More info: <https://diamas.org/>

⁸ OJS is operated by the Public Knowledge Project (PKP) in Canada and is also an OPERAS member.

Additionally, National Nodes have enabled translations for national communities early in the process, such as DOAS via the Mondaecus service. Furthermore, within the OPERAS framework, national languages are also prioritised to enhance accessibility. For instance, the GoTriple and VERA services are available in **nine different languages**, those of the National Nodes, making resources more accessible for local users or National Nodes being supporters in translating info and presentation material into their national languages.

We invite National Ministries to engage in a strategic dialogue on how we can strengthen the National Nodes, essential infrastructure supporting national research priorities and innovation. Through collaboration we can ensure the Nodes are well-positioned to deliver meaningful impact for the country's scholarly, national interest and societal progress.

▶ **3. Enhancing Open Scholarly Communication: Offering Training and Support - Key Services of OPERAS**

One of the key goals of the National Nodes is to provide training and support for OPERAS services. OPERAS' services catalogue enables SSH researchers, as well as students and publishers, libraries, journalists, and other key stakeholder groups to access, reuse, and exploit research results made fully open thanks to OPERAS. The National Nodes offer training and support for the following services.

▶ **GoTriple**

A multilingual platform tailored for the exploration of SSH research, offering tools that streamline the discovery of scholarly content and facilitate academic collaboration.

gotriple.eu

▶ **Pathfinder**

Designed to help researchers, editors and editorial managers find a solution to their editorial needs by presenting services as a catalogue, allowing to find service bundles for better editorial workflow.

pathfinder.operas-eu.org

▶ **Metrics**

Collects usage and impact metrics related to published Open Access books and allows their access, display, and analysis from a single access point.

metrics.operas-eu.org

Facilitates participatory research by allowing SSH researchers and other engaged stakeholders to find partners, appropriate tools, and funding opportunities to build projects and foster collaboration.

vera.operas-eu.org

Offering SSH researchers the ability to build an open conversation with socio-economic actors, particularly regarding societal challenges.

hypotheses.org

A quality assurance service allowing publishers to display information about their peer review procedures in a standardised way.

doabooks.org/en/librarians/prism

A platform to provide a collaborative environment for researchers and professionals to translate and edit scientific documents in multiple languages.

mondaecus.com

Comprehensive and flexible training focusing on specific audience needs, enhancing skills development, and fostering collaboration within the network, empowering members and communities to lead in Open Science practices, FAIR principles, OA Diamond publishing and other relevant topics.

Supports and advances innovative services and solutions for scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH), paving pathways for the development of OPERAS.

lab.operas-eu.org/

▶ OPERAS National Nodes Overview

Lead Institution: **Fundación Española para la Ciencia y Tecnología, F.S.P. (FECYT)** / Contact: virginia.pablo@fecyt.es
<https://calidadrevistas.fecyt.es/proyectos-y-colaboraciones>

Lead Institution: **Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV)** / Contact: anna.kotaviita@tsv.fi

Lead Institution: **CNRS—OpenEdition** / Contact: marina.cortes-aldaz@openedition.org
<https://operasfr.hypotheses.org/>

Lead Institution: **Max Weber Stiftung** / Contact: operas-ger@maxweberstiftung.de
<https://operas-ger.hypotheses.org/>

Lead Institution: **National Documentation Centre (EKT)** / Contact: ikatsaloulis@ekt.gr

Lead Institution: **University of Zadar** / Contact: operas-hr@unizd.hr

Lead Institution: **CNR-ILIESI** / Contact: enrico.pasini@cnr.it & elena.giglia@unito.it
<http://www.operas-it.org>

Lead Institution: **OAPEN Foundation** / Contact: stern@oapen.org

Lead Institution: **erih+** / Contact: Markus.Bang@hkdir.no

Lead Institution: **Institute of Literary Research Polish Academy of Sciences (IBL-PAN)** / Contact: otwartanauka@ibl.waw.pl
<https://operas.pl/>

Lead Institution: **University of Coimbra** / Contact: operas-pt@uc.pt
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/projetos/operas>

Lead Institution: **The Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (ZRC SAZU)** / Contact: ales.pogacnik@zrc-sazu.si
<https://zalozba.zrc-sazu.si/sl/strani/operassi>

Lead Institution: **Jisc** / Contact: frank.manista@jisc.ac.uk & anna.hughes@jisc.ac.uk
<https://www.jisc.ac.uk/get-involved/operas-uk-community>

OPERAS

open scholarly communication in the european
research area for social sciences and humanities

OPERAS AISBL

Quai aux Briques 76
1000 Brussels, Belgium

operas-eu.org

DOI

[10.5281/zenodo.16918868](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16918868)

**Funded by
the European Union**

*This policy brief was developed within
the OPERAS-PLUS project which has
received funding under the Horizon
Europe research and innovation pro-
gramme under Grant
Agreement No 101079608.*

Design

Nina Semolič
(ZRC SAZU)

